
Movement and Raising in Sasak Language: Transformation Study of Government and Binding Model

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to describe the application of movement and raising in the Sasak language. Movement and Raising are subtheories of Government and Binding (GB) (Chomsky, 1982). Movement and Raising theory is applied to examples: passivization, predicate raising and Wh-Movement in the Sasak language. Data collection was carried out using documentation and literature methods along with GB analysis instruments. The results and findings show that passivity can be seen in the thematic relationships determined by the argument structure of passive verbs that have a subject and passive verbs that do not have a subject. The absence of a subject is indicated by the symbol e (empty). Second, the noun phrase (NP) has the internal theta role of the prepositional phrase (PP) and the phrase gets the internal theta role directly from the head verb. From each example of NP displacement, there is an empty element marked with the symbol e in the position that NP has left. The findings show that coindexation marking is used to express that the empty element is coindexed with the NP in subject position. The empty category which marks the base position of the constituent that is moved to leave a trace is then termed a trace which is symbolized by the symbol t .

1. Introduction

Sasak Language/Bahasa Sasak (BS) is the language of the Sasak people, who dwell on the Indonesian island of Lombok. BS has four distinct dialects that are spoken throughout the Lombok regions. (Mahsun, 2019) states that language dialects are classified into four kinds, which are the dialects of meno-mene,

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ngeno-ngene, meriaq-meriqu, and kuto-kute. These dialects are basically related to one another. Then, structurally it has some of the uniqueness found in BS.

Firstly, the BS pattern has a tend to emphasize different word classes at the start without considering the structure of the clause itself. In other words, BS is more concerned with the context of the speech than the actual phrase form. Then, BS has a structure with pronoun tendencies that are optional, or even without the presence of an object. Consequently, objects in passive constructions do not require copulas, so the grammar created from the BS structure tends to be distinct from typical Indonesian language constructions. Another interesting process to observe is the process of forward and backward in the BS grammatical construction. The forwarding process, also known as promotion, is caused by the passage of valence between elements of a word. After undergoing a promotion, a noun-class word can become a verb, for example. Meanwhile, the process of turning back or also known as demotion is a change in the position and class of words from the actor changing into complements or classes of words that do not contribute due to the valence relationship between the clauses. The precedence and demotion in the BS are very common. It is also found in other languages. However, the factors that differentiate the process of leading and trailing tend to get grammatical interference from morphological processes, namely the affixation and removal of copulas in BS.

Secondly, BS has an unusual morphological process, hence there are distinctions between BS grammar and other languages. The distinguishing characteristic of BS is its tendency to prioritize the predicate in sentence structure. Morphology and word valence attachment facilitate the formulation of a clause in which the predicate appears at the beginning of the clause (Chomsky, 2018b). We need to know where the subject is that goes with the predicate. As the subject, the clause treats the reader or speaker of the BS as the agent performing the action, while the predicate occupies the place of prominence at the start of the sentence. Due of the predicate-centric prioritization process, BS often lacks a subject in spoken language, which can be confusing to listeners of other languages.

Third, the precedence and movement of words in BS is influenced by morphological dynamics, such as inflection and derivation. That is, the process of decreasing the form or function that can change the elements of the word actually results in the meaning of the process of forwarding or transferring words being changed and causing ambiguity of meaning. Then, the process of decreasing the function or class of words due to affixation in the inflection and derivation processes makes the words in phrases and clauses undergo a constituent blocking process in the movement process. This issue has also been mentioned by (Chomsky, 2017a); (Nisa, 2020) that there is a possibility of a blank spot process occurring in one of the clause elements.

Various additional exciting developments are also underway of Movement and Raising in the Sasak language is shown from syntactic relations. This means that there is a fundamental difference between the BS as the object of implementing the Theory of Government and Binding (TGB) with English Language/Bahasa Inggris (BI) as the object of study from the origin of the theory. For example, the void of elements in pronouns in the clause structure. BS grammar typically indicates the absence of a pronoun in a clause, despite the pronoun's obvious presence outside the text. If it is interpreted simply, it can lead to misunderstandings of its meaning. Therefore, it is assumed that pronouns are attempting to be highlighted in clauses through the context of the clause's speech in a single linguistic activity, such that the clause cannot be isolated from the narrative text. Language is essentially a communication tool that connects all elements that use it in daily life. Because of its numerous grammars, which means that its grammar is very reliant on the context in which it is used and the context in which the language is being used, BS makes for a very intriguing language instrument to study.

The process of movement and raising elements in the BS clause, certainly makes the BS grammatical valence process undergo a structural change. For this reason, the aim of this research is to describe the process of movement and raising of BS in the passivization structure, predicate raising, and movement of question words (Wh-Movement). These three aspects become a reference in

describing the transfer process of Noun Phrase (NP) Objects in passive verbs become NP Subjects in the passivization process in the BS. Then, a description of the NP movement in the process of predicate raising in BS. This process is in several studies (Setiawan & Mandala, 2021) states that passive verbs in grammar greatly influence the structure and valence of each linguistic element inherent in the language, such as subject, object and linguistic situation.

Passivization is intended to explain the function of a constituent having the potential to bind other constituents to one sentence. Then, raising as a promotion process that occurs due to constituent valence in BS grammar. The process of movement in the BS typically occurs in verbs, thus it is fascinating to describe this in sufficient complexity in the following section. In addition, this process is also known as inversion because the verb becomes a constituent that is put forward in a clause or sentence. The next process is the transfer of question words which has implications for the range of the question itself. That is, the position of the argument in a sentence that previously underwent a process of raising/inversion which made one constituent change its position and word class, from a Noun Phrase to a V-bar in one sentence/clause (Setiawan, 2022).

In the end, this research serves as a presenter of new things in the process of movement and raising in BS passive construction. In investigations of movement and raising in the BS, no relevance of earlier research has been identified, therefore it is likely that this work represents the most recent application of the theory Government and Binding Transformation Model (Chomsky, 2018a); (Setiawan, 2024a). The uniqueness found in this study is the process of movement and raising verbs and nouns in one sentence from active to passive structures. The impact of the process forms an inversion pattern on the passive structure in the BS. Thus, this research is expected to be able to provide a contemporary contribution related to Transformation studies, especially with the Government and Binding study model in BS.

2. Material and Method

Material

This study uses the theory of Generative Transformation by (Chomsky, 2017b) which was then adopted by certain practitioners of such generative schools such as (Hudson, 2020), (Horrocks, 2019), etc. Meanwhile, there are only a few other studies that use the generative transformation theory as a reference. The research that has been carried out includes, (1) "English Verb Valency Pattern in Padma Resort Legian Guest Reviews on TripAdvisor" (Suari, et al., 2022), (2) "Struktur Kalimat Bahasa Sasak: Ke Arah Penyusunan Bahasa Sasak Standar" (Paridi, et al., 2020), (3) "Asimilasi bunyi konsonan pada bahasa Bugis" (Jaya, 2019), and (4) "Tipe Klausa dan Perilaku Unsurnya dalam Bahasa Sasak" (Aridawati, 2015). The reference model was employed in all three experiments of Extended Standard Theory (Setiawan & Mandala, 2021). Researches that used the reference to the theory of Generative Transformation of the Government and Binding model (GB) (Chomsky, 1982) was the study of "Struktur Frase Bahasa Sasak: Sebuah Kajian Berdasarkan Teori X-bar" (Paridi, 2002). Promnominal Trace dalam Bahasa Sasak: Kajian Teori Transformasi. The study "Struktur Frase Bahasa Sasak: Sebuah Kajian Berdasarkan Teori X-bar". This study discovered that: (a) X-bar theory sufficient to describe the structure of the Sasak language phrase although there is still an affix system that blocks the occurrence of Wh-Movement, (b) all Sasak phrases follow X-bar format (c) The INFL system and the AGR system in Sasak are indeed very different from the English system where GB theory is being tested. With these findings, it is advised that more research be conducted on various linguistic features of the Sasak language and the archipelago's languages in general. Based on the preceding investigations, it is proven that this research focuses on describing the process of movement and increasing in BS, which has never been evaluated by earlier research. Thus, the position of this research is as a presenter of new things that have not been discussed by previous

researchers and seeks to describe in detail the system of movement and raising in the Sasak language, hereinafter abbreviated as BS.

3. Method

This study uses a qualitative method. Qualitative methods produce descriptive data regarding the phenomena of spoken or written texts, behavior or social linguistic practices, and can be observed from the subject itself. Qualitative methods are intended to describe the process of Movement and Raising in language. The focus of the research was carried out on the Sasak language (BS) with the selected sub dialect being the Selaparang – Pejanggik dialect. The reason is that the Selaparang – Pejanggik dialect is a standard variety of BS that can be spoken by every speaker of the Sasak tribe on Lombok Island. The form of dialect spoken by speakers is often called a dialect ngeno – ngene [ŋəno - ŋənz].

Data collection uses the method of listening and introspection. The listening method is a linguistic research method used to obtain data by listening to speakers or users of the language itself. (Mahsun, 2014); (Sudaryanto, 2018) emphasized that the listening method is very effective for examining language and its use, especially KBG in society. The listening technique used is the free-involvement technique of speaking, recording, and taking notes. These three techniques are used by patterning and categorizing the data, so that the data is ready for analysis. The strategies carried out in the process of listening to BSas users include: setting criteria for speech partners, interacting naturally (without settings), and interacting by being directly involved in conversations with partners. To determine the interlocutor in the process of obtaining data samples, several conditions are required, as stated (Mahsun, 2014) as follows: a) the speaker is a native BSas speaker, b) the partner can speak Indonesian fluently, c) the partner is physically healthy, d) Partners aged 17 – 50 years, and d) Partners have low mobilization. Furthermore, the recording and recording process is carried out by researchers carefully to examine every data that has been listened to, including phonetic markers and accents, emphasis, or intonation. The introspection method is a linguistic research method that seeks to examine field data from the perspective of the researcher as a native speaker from the data obtained. This method according to (Siska, et al., 2023) is very effective in selecting data.

The data obtained was then validated based on the theory of Government and Binding Transformation model instrument in the study of the transformation of the government and binding model. This step is intended to ensure that the data analysis is in accordance with the objectives and results of the research. In that sense, the validation process based on research instruments is intended so that the data does not raise doubts and generates reader trust. The following are examples of the Movement and Raising instruments below.

Scheme 1 Flow Chart of the Analysis of Movement and Raising in Sasak language

In investigating Movement and Raising in the Sasak language, Explanation of Scheme 1 involves numerous lines of analysis, those are (Cresswel, 2022):

*Movement and Raising In Sasak Language:
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(Khairul Paridi, Irma Setiawan, Burhanuddin, Siti Rohana Hariana Intiana)*

- 1) Reduction stage, namely the analysis stage, includes the meticulous identification of research data, which is then patterned or classified depending on the identity of the data gathered.
- 2) Presentation stage, in which the researcher performs data segmentation in the form of analysis based on the research instrument. This section describes the Movement and Raising analysis method in Sasak language using X-Bar analysis.
- 3) The verification stage, in which the researcher completes the previously carried out identification and segmentation operations. Movement and Raising analysis can be done on specified data samples during this operation.

4. Result and Discussion

According to the issues outlined in the introduction, the BS data provides an interesting theoretical testing ground to investigate. The following discussion includes data in the BS, from NP category data that experience movement in sentences. As previously stated, sentence elements that occupy a certain position at the D-Structure level can be moved to a certain position at the S-Structure level. The movement started with the Alpha movement, passivation, and raising. The most common movement is Alpha-Movement. Movement is a derivation of a category. The case of alpha movement in BS will be discussed in this section. Then, the data analysis process is based on the GB theory by looking at movement and raising, of course it has gone through several stages of triangulation. This stage confirms that the data being analyzed is valid and reliable data, so that some research results can be found. First, the data is documented and obtained through library sources. Second, the data is combined and patterned based on the researcher's self-perception as a comparison filter. This is possible because the researcher is a native BSAs speaker.

From the documentation data that has been done, found several data that have gone through a triangulation process. This data includes passivation, raising and wh-movement. Several sentence analyzes show that every sentence always relies on two levels of syntactic representation, namely Deep Structure (D-structure) and Surface Structure (S-structure). To explain the Alpha movement operation in question, here will be an example of the process "passivation", "raising" dan "wh-movement" in BS as follows.

4.1 Passivation in Sasak Language

To explain the process of movement in passivation, consider the two examples of BS sentences (1) below

- (1) a. *Kepeng sino tebait siq Inaq.*
 'uang itu diambil oleh ibu'.
 (The money was taken by mom)
- b. *Inaq mbait kepeng sino.*
 'ibu mengambil uang itu'.
 (Mom took the money)

In the phrase (5a) the verb *tebait* 'diambil'/'taken' is a passive form. If (5a) is contradicted by sentence (5b) which uses the verb *mbait* 'mengambil'/'took' in the active form, it will be seen that NP *kepeng sino* 'uang itu'/'the money' As the subject of the passive sentence, it has similarities with the internal argument of the verb in the active sentence *mbait* 'mengambil'/'took'. Thus it can be said that NP *kepeng sino* 'uang itu'/'that money' as internal theta role by the verb *mbait* 'mengambil'/'took' because the core of the PP directly binds *kepeng sino* 'uang itu'/'the money'. This is in line with what was stated by (Haegemen, 2020).

Passive verbs have characteristics, they cannot provide a structural case, objective-case to their complements. Therefore, if NP *kepeng sino* 'uang itu'/'the money' remains in the position of the object, then the position will conflict with the filter-case. It appears that NP *kepeng sino* 'uang itu'/'the money' take the place of a subject who has achieved INFL nominative case. This proves that case filters only apply at the surface-structure level, while at the Deep-Structure level, the noun phrase *kepeng sino* 'uang itu'/'the money'

is in its base position which cannot accept any case. Ka-rena kata araq 'ada'/'true that' didn't get a case, then the sentence above becomes unacceptable, as happened in sentence (2) below.

- (2) *(araq) tebait kepeng sino siq Inaq.
 'Ada diambil uang itu oleh ibu'
 ((It is true that) the money taken by mom)

As seen in example (2) above it appears that NP kepeng sino 'uang itu'/'the money' occupy the position of the subject who has received the INFL nominative case. This proves that the case filter only applies at the Surface-structure level, while at the Deef-structure level the noun phrase kepeng sino 'uang itu'/'the money' is in the base position which can't accept any case. Because the word araq 'ada'/'It is true that' not getting the case, then sentence (2) above becomes unacceptable.

- (3) adine tebeng kepeng isiq papuq ne
 'Adik dikasi uang oleh nenek'
 (Sister given money by her grandma)

N in sentence (3) has the role of agent of theta which functions to bind the constituents around it. The theta function is local, of course, making the sentence process naturally in grammatical interactions. That is, the passive process of the verb tebeng is certainly marked by the presence of the particle te-. However, from the perspective of movement and raising the passive structure in a sentence does not have to shift the valence of its constituents, but instead changes the direction of action and the target of action of the variables in the sentence.

4.2 Predicate Raising in Sasak Language

NP-movement does not only occur in passive sentence formations, but the movement of NP also occurs in the front of the predicate because of the form of the verb "raising". To explain the raising operation, consider the representation of the sentence below.

- (4) Cerita sino tesaduq siq amane.
 'Cerita itu dipercayai oleh ayahnya'
 (The story was believed by his father)
- (5) Ulpa tesaduq oah ngilangang barang bukti sino.
 'Ulpa dipercayai telah menghilangkan barang bukti itu'
 (Ulpa was believed to have lost the evidence)

The two examples of sentences above, each have an inner structure and a surface structure. The Deef Structure and Surface Structure (6) are (6a) and (6b).

- (6) a. [IP e[r [tesaduq [NP cerita sino] siq amana]]]].
 dipercayai cerita itu oleh ayahnya'
 b. (It was believed the story by his father)
 c. [IP [Cerita sino [r VP tesaduq [ei] siq ama ne]]]].
 'Cerita itu dipercayai oleh ayahnya'
 (The story was believed by his father)

The noun phrase cerita sino 'cerita itu'/'the story' in (6a) received theta marking directly from the verb tesaduq 'dipercayai'/'was believed'. The empty subject position marked with the symbol e is because passive verbs cannot give the external theta role to NP cerita sino 'cerita itu'/'the story', therefore he must move into the position of the subject to be able to get the case marking of finite inflection.

Unlike the passive verb in example (7), the passive verb in example (8) can be modified in such a way that the sentence is in the form (9) below.

- (7) Tesaduq [CP kanjeq [IP Ulpa oah ngilangan barang bukti sino]].
 'dipercayai bahwa Ulpa telah menghilangkan barang bukti itu'
 (It was believed that Ulpa have lost the evidence)

Another example in the BS that can be used as an example of NP displacement is the raising below.

(8) [IP Ulpa i [VP teparan [IP ie oah nyedaq barang bukti sino]]].

'Ulpa dipercayai telah merusak barang bukti itu'
(Ulpa was believed to have lost the evidence)

(9) [IP Ulpa i [VP ruene [IP ie oah nyedaq barang bukti sino]]].

'Ulpa rupanya dia telah merusak barang bukti itu'
(Ulpa seems to have lost the evidence)

Example sentences (12) and (13) show that the subject in a lower clause is withdrawn from its initial position and then moved to the position of the subject in a higher position in the matrix clause.

4.3 Movement of Question Words (Wh-Movement) in Sasak Language

The following is an explanation of the transfer of question words in the BS below.

(10)

- a. Yaumul gen ngelek adine
'Yaumul akan memanggil adiknya'.
(Yaumul will call his brother)
- b. Gen Yaumul ngelek adine?
'Akan Yaumul panggil adiknya'.
(Will Yaumul call his brother?)
- c. Yaumul gen ngelek sai ?
'Yaumul akan memanggil siapa'.
(Yaumul will call who?)
- d. Sai si gen Yaumul kelek?
'Siapa yang akan Yaumul panggil'.
(Who will be called by Yaumul)
- e. Ndeq ku taoq apa Yaumul gen ngelek adine?
'Saya tidak tau apakah Yaumul akan memanggil adiknya'
(I do not know if Yaumul will call his brother)
- f. Ndeq ku taoq [sai gen Yaumul kelek?]
'Saya tidak tau siapa akan Yaumul panggil'.
(I do not know who will Yaumul call)

Looking at all the sentences in example (10) above, it can be seen that the external argument is the verb ngelek 'memanggil' is NP Yaumul while the internal argument is NP adine 'adiknya'/'his brother'. Syntactically the external argument of the verb ngelek 'memanggil'/'call' represented by a noun phrase in its position as a subject, while the internal argument is represented by the direct object of the sentence's verb, namely a noun phrase which is dominated by V' (V-bar). Furthermore, the inner structure (10a) is the representation (11) while the surface structure is the representation in (12) below.

(11)

(12)

Diagram (11) above shows that the word *gen* is dominated by INFL as also in diagram (12). Inverted order as happened in example (10c) occurs when the word *gen* moved from the original position dominated by the node INFL to a position dominated by the C node. With this kind of analysis, the surface structure of sentence (10c) will be like the tree diagram below.

- (13) *Gen Yaumul ngelek adine?*
 'Akan Yaumul memanggil adiknya?'
 (Will Yaumul call his brother?)

(14)

Gap which occurs as a result of word movement gen 'akan'/'will' to C position marked by e symbol. The position relationship left by the word gen 'akan'/'will' and the moved element is indicated by the presence of coindexation because it is the element that undergoes movement head to other head position, then example (10b) is the example of Head-to head movement.

In its form as an interrogative sentence, in example (13) and (14) it is also called echo question which is formed by replacing one of the constituents of the sentence with a question word sai 'siapa'/'who'. The question word sai realize the internal argument of the verb nglek 'memanggil'/'call'. As the echo question, then the representation is in example (15) below.

(15) [CP [IP Yaumul gen nglek [adin e]]] ?
 'Yaumul akan memanggil adiknya'
 (Yaumul will call his brother?)

The equation by representation (10c) as echo question is a logical consequence of moving elements in a sentence of echo question.

Next, a representation will be displayed Deef Structure and Surface Structure in (14d). The question that might arise from this representation is: what is the external argument of the verb nglek 'memanggil'/'call' embodied?; How the verb nglek 'memanggil'/'call' juga assigns the theta role to noun phrases sai 'siapa'/'who' which he does not master, and what is the process of giving the accusative case to the noun phrase sai.

In order to answer the questions above, first, the representation of the structure in the sentence (10d) as (16) below.

(16) [CP [IP Yaumul gen [nglek [sai ?]]].
 'Yaumul akan memanggil siapa'
 (Yaumul will call who?)

The representation (16) above, is a form of representation Deef Structure of the word in (10d). It is the same representation with Deef Structure echo question above. And, on the Surface structure level above, the word gen 'akan'/'will' at the example in (10d) moved to a position dominated by C node. In other words, NP sai moved to NP position, Spec. which is directly dominated by the CP node. Look at the tree diagram (17) below.

(17)

The symbol *i/e* denotes the position left by the noun phrase *sai*. In this case the coindexation connects *e* with the moved constituents. The diagram above shows that the theta marking and case-marking problems of the question words *sai* can be answered. Thus, it can be said that the verb *ngelek* 'memanggil'/'call' assigns the role of the internal theta and the accusative case to the NP that is in the internal VP position marked with the symbol *e/i*.

From the description above, three examples of movement can be seen in NP. From each example of the movement of NP it can be concluded that there is an empty element (empty) to the position left by NP. The empty element is indexed by the NP at the subject position, as indicated by the coindexation designation. The empty category (empty) which marked the base position of the constituent being transferred is termed a trace which is denoted by the symbol (*t*). Next, consider the following example.

The necessity for a movement of NP in sentences (18a and 18b) following is driven by the fact that if the NP does not move then he will lose the case (Caseless) and of course contrary to case-filter principle. Therefore statements (18a) and (18b) require further explanation, as exemplified below.

(18)

- a. Ineq percaya [VP kanjeq anakne gen menang].
'Ibu percaya bahwa anaknya akan menang'
(Mom believed that her son would win)
- b. Terpercayaq siq Ineq [CP kanjeq anakne gen menang].
'Dipercaya oleh Ibu bahwa anaknya akan menang'
(It was believed by mom that her son will win)
- c. [CP Kanjeq anakne gen menang] tepercayaq siq Ineq].
'Bahwa anaknya akan menang dipercaya oleh Ibu'
(The fact that her son will win was believed by mom)

In the example above, it can be seen that the verb *percaya* (18a) has a clause complement, whereas in (18b) the verb has been changed to a passive verb, thus the complement does not move. In example (18c) the complement clause is moved so that it affects the CP and NP. This shows that the movement is not obligatory because CP is not equal to NP, therefore it does not get a case filter. Thus, CP can be in the base position.

In example (18c) it can be seen that the move can occur to the empty position (without getting the theta marker (nontheta mark position)). Intuitively, this movement characteristic makes sense because if an NP

moves to a position already filled by another NP (theta mark position), there will be a collision between the two NPs. Compare with the example below.

(19)

- a. [IP Toni [VP mantol Wir]
Toni memukul Wir
(Toni hit Wir)

In example (19) above it can be seen that the verb mantok 'memukul'/'hit' got the internal and external NP argument. NP Wir received the internal theta role and NP Toni get the external theta role of the verb mantok. If NP Wir moved to the position occupied by NP Toni then the construction will occur as below.

- (20) [IP Wir [VP mantok t/i]
Wir memukul
(Wir hits)

In the example data (20) above, NP Wir received nominative case then form a chain with its trace. On the S-surface level verb mantok will assign the internal theta role to NP Wir chain. If the verb mantok gave the external theta role to NP Wir then the chain Wir will have two theta roles. If so, it would be against the principle of theta criterion. If the verb mantok 'memukul'/'hit' do not gave the role to external theta, theta criterion principle also not fulfilled because one of its theta roles is not given (Radford. A, 2017).

The explanation shows that it is impossible for an NP to move to a position that has been occupied by another NP. This proves that there will be no verb that can give two theta roles simultaneously in an NP, both internal theta roles and external theta roles. Another claim states that the NP always moves to a position that allows it to accept cases. Consider the following example (21).

- (21) Ruene [kanjeq cerita sino tepercayaq siq ama-na]
'Rupanya bahwa cerita itu dipercayai oleh ayahnya'
(Apparently that story was believed by his father)

- (22) Cerita sino ruene tepercayaq siq amane
'Cerita itu rupanya dipercayai oleh ayahnya'
(The story apparently believed by his father)

The word ruene in example (21) above received an NP internal argument and have no external argument NP. The verb percayaq the subordinate clause is passive, and the verb gives the role of internal theta to NP cerita sino while the NP cerita sino in sentence (22) is the internal argument of the verb percayaq. The subject position of percayaq not filled in level Deep Structure even though the principle Extended Projection Principle (EPP) require the position to be filled (Radford. A, 2017). In the base position of NP cerita sino cannot be given a case by the verb. Therefore, he had to move to a position that would allow him to accept cases. The NP subject position in the subordinate clause cannot be the landing site for the movement because at this position an NP will lose the case (Caseless). This proves that words like ruene 'rupanya'/'apparently' cannot be nominative case. Look at the example sentence (27) below.

- (23) *Taufiq ruene kanjeq tepercaya siq amana.
'Taufiq rupanya bahwa dipercaya oleh ayahnya'
(Taufiq apparently to have been trusted by his father)

NP subject position the lower clause should be empty, NP Taufiq moved to the subject position of a higher clause because in this position it will get the nominative case. The non-acceptance of sentence (27) above proves that an NP cannot jump over the NP that are present in the same clause and move to a higher position of the subject of the clause. Thus, the movement of an NP must be local.

Movement of NP in Bsas in the local context means that the process of movement and raising does not require a systematic valence factor in grammar. If NP is forced in the context of sentence (28), it will certainly result in particle demotion which causes the status of the word that is experiencing movement to become chemouer (unemployed).

4.4 BS Passivation Construction

Passivation of BS, raises several examples of categories in word valence. The function of NP in the passive voice has the role of theta in the internal valence of the word itself. Like, in the word case (a) *Kepeng sino tebait siq Inaq* “uang itu diambil oleh ibu”/“they money was taken by mom” has a passive construction, then it is changed in the active construction of the word *tebait* > ‘mbait “diambil/taken > mengambil/took” in the phrase (b) *Inaq mbait kepeng sino* “ibu mengambil uang itu”/“Mom took the money”.

To maintain the parallels between (a) and (b) with the hypothesis of the role of internal theta given directly by the core of a phrase, a movement analysis is developed from an element of a sentence that has a pattern such as (a) and (b).

The description above shows that the Deef structure (D-structure) seen from the thematic relationship is determined by the structure of the argument verb *tebait* ‘diambil’/‘taken’ differ from the word *bait* ‘ambil’/‘took’ which has no subject. The absence of the subject in sentence (a) above is indicated by the symbol *e* (empty). The noun phrase *kepeng sino* ‘uang itu’/‘the money’ in sentence (b) is the internal theta role of PP and the phrase gets the internal theta role directly from the main verb. With the process of permutation from the position of the object to the position of the subject, a string of sentences (Setiawan & Mandala, 2021).

The valence process in movement and raising that NP *kepeng sino* ‘uang itu’/‘the money’ has moved from the VP internal theta position to the external theta subject position. Such movement is called an NP movement. As a result of this movement, the internal position originally filled by the phrase at the Deef-structure level becomes vacant (empty). The empty element is marked with the symbol *e* (empty). the relationship between this and the NP is transferred by indexation which is marked with the symbol *i* (indexation). This symbol is used for the derivational process of the original sentence being analyzed. This is in line with what was stated by (Lasnik, H., 2017).

In contrast to the string of words in the sentence (6), which is often referred to as an arche-type (underlying-order) in Deef-structure level, and at the Surface-structure level as in (6) it is often referred to as a derived pattern (derived-order) which is the result of the (6) modification. Furthermore, NP *kepeng sino* ‘uang itu’/‘the money’ in (21) referred to as a derived-subject, not a deep-structure subject. The position of the Deef-structure noun phrases like this especially its position as an object is known as the base-position. Thus, it can be said that NP *kepeng sino* ‘uang itu’/‘the money’ is based-generated in its position as an object with a passive verb form *tebait* ‘diambil’/‘taken’.

The brief description of the NP movement above shows that the syntactic analysis of a sentence must refer to two levels of syntactic representation, the Deef-structure (D-structure) and the Surface structure (S-structure). Deef structure relates to the predicate-arguments and thematic richness of a sentence, while surface-structure representation relates to the surface ordering of the constituents of a sentence.

4.5 BS Raising System

NP movement in the valence of the sentence called NP – Movement as a process of promotion of a word element from previously being the target of action turned into a giver of action. This construction will differ according to terminology of (Setiawan & Mandala, 2021); (Setiawan, 2024b) who states that the lexical valence of a sentence has no correlation between active and passive structures. Active – passive constructions do not have a lexical relationship, but functional valence makes the two constructions cross-reference (construal). In a more functional view, (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2019) suggests that changes in the lexical structure of NP make the function of the actor turn into a goal, meaning that the active - passive construction makes the demotional actor a victim in the valence of the sentence itself, on the contrary, the process of putting the victim forward is no longer possible because NP actor > goal will change to chemours

(non-functional in sentence valence). Then, the process of raising generally occurs in the predicate, resulting in NP.

The actor has an active action with the system V-bar through the process of raising constituents in the form of predicate copula gen which is more correlated with modality. (Setiawan, 2019) argues that modality as the level of possibility of the activity being carried out or not being carried out. The presence of these modalities makes the sentence have a level of tendency in the realization of the predicate. An interesting thing that needs to be a common concern, is that the system of prioritizing the BS predicate has a modality tendency, so that the realization of actor's actions towards goals. The realization of the action shown through the actor, the predicate undergoes movement in order it becomes an inversion construction.

4.6 Movement and Raising Pattern BS

Movement and publishing word elements after going through the process of mobilizing between elements in the context of a text makes one word class shift its function in the grammar of a language. This process tends to occur in interrogative sentences. The pattern of movement that occurs in interrogative sentences BS can be seen that the elements that have been moved leave traces on the landing site. The elements that are moved are called antecedents. The first reason in determining the trace of an NP is generally based on the projection principle of theta theory and case theory.

From the previous description it is known that the filter case is not an independent grammatical principle that Ulpa's argument NP appears in chain t/i Ulpa. The position filled by NP Ulpa head and which is filled by trace is called foot in mentioned chain. The subject in the subordinate clause indicates a theta position. This position becomes transparent in the chain t/i Ulpa because the chain contains a case marked position, where the position of the matrix clause that received nominative case from I finite.

If this theta theory is applied at the level of deep-structure and surface structure, it will appear that the deep structure is a representation of the lexical richness of a sentence. This means that all syntactic arguments of a predicate must be spelled out. The surface structure shows the results of the transparency of the movement of a sentence element. This can make it clear that a structure that maintains the principles of movement results in a conclusion that the movement of a sentence element will leave a trace because all positions that appear at the level of the inner structure must be maintained (Koopman, 2020).

Thus, based on this discussion, the implications of the study of the Transformation of the Government and Binding model occur in the previous theory, namely, structural theory explains that there is no scientific argument why a sentence element such as an NP object moves to another position, for example, moving to the NP Subject position in an active sentence, what motivates the move, in other theories there is no scientific explanation why passive and active sentences occur. The GLB theory in the Movement and Raising sub-theory in the case of classification and prioritization of predicates can provide scientific arguments. That way a scientific theory should be able to explain a phenomenon with scientific arguments. This has not been done before. In other words, the GB transformation theory has elegant explanatory power.

In accordance with the principles of GB that the internal structure of grammar in the BS consists of subsystems of elements, each of which is autonomous. Thus, the complexity of the syntax can be simplified with the existing subsystems in the theory. One of the important claims of GB theory is that every language construct that appears must be consistent with the principles of this theory. In other words, these principles function as well-formedness conditions of a language construction. With these language principles according to GB Theory, BSAs rules, such as transformation rules involving special constructions of passive rules, interrogative formation is no longer needed. All of these rules or rules have been simplified in order that the various constructions can be produced through the basic principles contained in GB theory such as X-bar which contains theta element, Case, Control, Bounding, Binding and Government.

5. Conclusion

Several conclusions can be drawn from the above descriptions and examples. First, in GB theory (Walee, J. A., Mezher, Y. S., & Mohsen, 2022) sentence structure in a language has two levels of syntactic representation, those are the Deep-Structure level and the Surface-Structure level. The two levels of representation are linked through a transfer transformation process (movement) of a sentence element. Sentence elements that occupy a certain position on D-Structure level can be moved to a certain position on the S-Structure level. This transformation process is operated by the following movement and raising. Furthermore, Movement and Raising applied to examples: passivation, predicate raising and question word movement (Wh-Movement) in the Sasak language.

Passivation can be seen in the thematic relationships determined by the argument structure of passive verbs that have a subject and passive verbs that don't have a subject. The absence of a subject is indicated by a symbol *e* (empty). Second, the noun phrase (NP) is the internal theta role of prepositional phrases (PP) and the phrase gets the internal theta role directly from the core verb (head verb). From each of these NP movement examples, there is an empty element (empty) marked with a symbol *e* in a position that has been left by NP. The coindexation designation is used to indicate that the empty element is coindexed with NP in subject position. Empty category (empty) which marks the base position of the moved constituent leaving a trail then termed a trace which is symbolized by the symbol (*t*).

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